

COLCHICINE-INDUCED MUTAGENESIS ON GROWTH AND YIELD CHARACTERS OF A COWPEA VARIETY

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ABSTRACT

The induced mutation techniques have been used successfully in various crops, but their application in cowpea breeding is limited. This research evaluates the effects of colchicine treatment on the growth and yield attributes of the cowpea variety 'Bewehe'. The objective was to assess the mutagenic influence of colchicine on the growth and yield characteristics of cowpea, examining various concentrations (0.00%, 0.05%, 0.10%, and 0.15%) and exposure durations (0, 2, 4, and 6 hours) within the M1 generation. The experiment was a four x four factorial arrangement within a completely randomized design, incorporating three replications. The colchicine treatment had a significant effect ($p < 0.05$) on most growth and yield parameters assessed, except the number of main branches and the length of terminal leaves. The most favourable growth conditions were at a concentration of 0.05% for 2 hours. The highest yield was at a concentration of 0.15% for 6 hours. Colchicine treatment notably enhanced seed weight, with peak values achieved at the 6-hour treatment duration and 0.15% concentration. There were significant positive correlations between survival percentage and germination percentage, between the number of leaves and days to first flowering, between 100 seed weight and the number of leaves, and between 100 seed weight and germination percentage. The colchicine treatment improved seed weight and established strong positive correlations among growth and yield traits. Early flowering positively correlated with lower germination, shorter plant height, and reduced survival. Colchicine treatment in cowpeas results in complex interactions between vegetative and reproductive traits, highlighting the need for optimal treatment conditions to balance growth and yield outcomes.

Keywords: germination percentage, length of terminal leaves, number of main branches.

INTRODUCTION

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) is a vital legume extensively cultivated in developing countries, particularly in tropical regions. It serves as an affordable and essential source of dietary protein, playing a significant role in the livelihoods of millions, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, where it is a staple food crop. In countries like Nigeria, cowpea is a primary

source of plant-based protein. This multifunctional crop not only provides nutrition for human consumption but also serves as livestock feed and a reliable income source for farmers and traders. As a multipurpose legume, cowpea provides edible leaves, green pods, and seeds that are rich in nutrients. The nutritional composition of cowpea seeds includes approximately 24.3% protein, 63.6%

carbohydrates, 1.9% fat, 6.3% fibre, and 8–9% moisture content (Singh *et al.*, 2021a). The seed coat contains flavonoids, which are antioxidants that help protect human cells from oxidative stress (Dillard and German, 2000). It is consumed in several forms, including grains, green pods, and fresh leaves. Due to its wide range of uses, nutritional benefits, and good storage properties, cowpea is a crucial part of farming systems in West Africa (Singh *et al.*, 2021b). Moreover, cowpea has the potential to alleviate food security issues in developing countries, making it a valuable resource for combating food shortages (Fatokun *et al.*, 2018).

Cowpea yields remain low, especially in marginal areas, largely due to the limited adaptability of existing varieties to diverse growing conditions. The varying requirements for plant type, seed type, maturity, and usage across different regions add complexity to breeding programs. Additionally, the crop's self-pollinating nature restricts its genetic variability, posing further challenges to improvement efforts (Dugje *et al.*, 2009). To address these yield limitations, induced mutation has emerged as a promising strategy to enhance genetic variability and develop cultivars with improved economic traits. This technique has been successfully used to introduce variability and improve desirable characteristics in cowpeas and other crops. Genetic variability is crucial for crop improvement, providing the necessary diversity to develop new varieties that exhibit better growth, higher yields, increased stress tolerance, and reduced agronomic input needs. Induced mutation, which involves altering the genetic material of an organism, can be applied to seeds and vegetatively propagated crops, making it a valuable tool for both scientific research and commercial agriculture. The effectiveness of any mutagen in plant breeding depends on its ability to induce beneficial changes efficiently while minimizing adverse effects (Jankowicz-

Cieslak *et al.*, 2017). Among various chemical mutagens, colchicine stands out for its notable effects (Sattin *et al.*, 2019). Derived from the plant *Colchicum autumnale*, colchicine disrupts microtubule formation during mitosis, leading to dynamic instability. It has been widely utilized in plant breeding to alter ploidy levels, which can result in beneficial mutations. Colchicine interferes with the orientation and structure of mitotic fibres, inhibiting mitosis, which is crucial for chromosome segregation. While polyploidy can be harmful in animal cells, it is generally well tolerated in plants, often leading to larger, more robust, and faster-growing individuals (Sattin *et al.*, 2019). As a result, colchicine-induced polyploidy is frequently employed in breeding programs to create genetic variability, resulting in the development of several high-yielding crop variants. Colchicine is recognized as one of the most effective tools for inducing and enhancing genetic variability in food crops within a relatively short timeframe (Sattin *et al.*, 2019). This study aims to investigate the effects of varying concentrations of colchicine on cowpea to improve their growth and yield-related traits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area and planting materials

The research was carried out at the Teaching and Research Farm, Department of Agricultural Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Offa, Kwara State, Nigeria. The study utilized a cowpea variety known as "Bewehe," procured from Oja Oba Market in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Seed treatment procedures

Seeds were initially soaked in distilled water for three hours, after which they were drained and allowed to air dry. Subsequently, the seeds were treated (at room temperature) with varying concentrations of colchicine: 0.00% (control), 0.05%, 0.10%, and 0.15%, across

different soaking durations: 0 hours (control), 2 hours, 4 hours, and 6 hours. Following treatment, seeds were rinsed in running tap water for six minutes.

Experimental design

The experiment was designed as a 4 x 4 factorial arrangement within a completely randomized design, with three replications. The factors included colchicine concentrations (0.00%, 0.05%, 0.10%, 0.15%) and soaking durations (0, 2, 4, and 6 hours). Seeds were sown in plastic pots, each with a 5-litre capacity filled with sandy loam soil. Three seeds were planted per pot, and each treatment was replicated three times. Sixteen pots per replicate resulted in forty-eight pots for the entire experiment. Plants were later thinned to two per pot, and standard agronomic practices such as irrigation, pest management, and weed control were employed.

Data collection

Data were collected and recorded on germination percentage at 20 days after planting. Plant height was measured from the base to the height of the first tassel branch at 8 weeks post-planting. The number of leaves per plant was counted 7 weeks after planting as leaf count. Terminal leaf length was measured in centimetres at 7 weeks after planting. Terminal leaf breadth was measured in centimetres at 7 weeks after planting. Number of main branches was counted at 7 weeks after planting. Nodes on the main branch were counted at 7 weeks after planting. Survival percentage was determined at plant maturity. Days to first flowering were recorded from planting to first flowering. Pods per plant were counted at maturity. Seeds per pod were recorded at maturity, and weights of 100 seeds were measured in grammes at maturity.

Data analysis

Data for the twelve plant traits were compiled and analysed using Analysis of

Variance (ANOVA) with Genstat Discovery Edition 3. Differences among means were determined using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test. Analysis of the effects of interaction between treatment duration and treatment concentration on growth and yield traits was done. Correlation analysis was also carried out to determine the relationship between the parameters.

RESULTS

Effect of colchicine on cowpea growth and yield

Analysis of growth characters of cowpea

Table 1 shows the mean square values for various growth attributes of cowpea. The findings revealed that the duration of colchicine exposure significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced several growth factors, including the number of leaves, nodes on the main branch, percentage germination, plant height, survival rate, and terminal leaf width. However, there was no significant variation ($p > 0.05$) in the number of main branches and terminal leaf length. The concentration levels and interaction between treatment duration and concentration levels of colchicine significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected the number of leaves, percentage germination, plant height, and survival rate while showing no significant effect on the number of main branches, nodes on the main branch, terminal leaf width, and terminal leaf length. Descriptive statistics (mean, range, standard deviation, and coefficient of

variation) further demonstrated notable differences. This analysis underscores the importance of treatment duration and concentration in influencing specific growth traits.

Table 1: Mean squares of growth characters of cowpea

SV	DF	NLV	NMB	NNB	PCG (%)	PHT(cm)	SVP (%)	TLB(cm)	TLL(cm)
R	2	3.56	4.40	0.58	208.30	16.82	91.15	0.34	1.99
T	3	115.14**	0.13 ^{ns}	6.17**	5047.70**	44.31**	3368.06**	2.77**	6.93 ^{ns}
C	3	156.47**	0.47 ^{ns}	1.17 ^{ns}	4457.50**	31.66**	4270.83**	0.64 ^{ns}	12.52 ^{ns}
T x C	9	18.08**	0.32 ^{ns}	0.89 ^{ns}	776.90**	4.49 ^{ns}	671.30**	0.35 ^{ns}	3.40 ^{ns}
Error	30	1.36	0.48	0.25	125.00	2.70	63.37	0.16	1.99
Total	47								
SD		4.67	0.77	0.91	29.01	2.85	25.70	0.64	1.80
CV		1.8%	10.2%	7.3%	19.7%	8.8%	15.3%	5.6%	11.1%
Range		14	3	3	75	9.7	75	2.8	10.4

NLV-Number of leaves; NMB- Number of main branches; NNB- Number of nodes on main branch; PCG- Percentage germination (%); PHT- Plant height (cm); SVP- Survival percentage (%); TLB- Terminal leaf breadth (cm); TLL- Terminal leaf length (cm); **- Means highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ns - Means not significant at $p < 0.001$; SV- Sources of variation; R- Replication; T- Treatment duration (hrs); C- Concentration of colchicine (%); SD- Standard deviation and CV Coefficient of variation (%).

Analysis of grain yield characters for cowpea

Table 2 outlines the mean square values for cowpea grain yield characteristics. The results show that the timing of first flowering, pod count per plant, seed weight, and seeds per pod were significantly affected ($p < 0.05$) by the duration of

treatment and concentration levels. Significant interactions between treatment duration and concentration levels were observed for the timing of first flowering, pod count per plant, and seeds per pod, though seed weight remained unaffected by these interactions, indicating that seed weight was affected independently.

Table 2: Mean squares of yield characters of cowpea

SV	DF	DFF	NPP	SDW(gm)	SPP
R	2	0.25	0.52	0.01	0.15
T	3	37.14**	26.08**	1.82**	25.25**
C	3	29.92**	33.74**	1.12**	27.92**
T x C	9	5.19**	9.28**	0.20 ^{ns}	8.94**
Error	30	0.83	0.77	0.06	0.59
Total	47				
SD		2.41	2.47	0.51	2.34
CV		1.6%	4.3%	1.1%	3.8%
Range		8	12	1.8	11

DFF- Days to first flowering; NPP-Number of pods per plant; SDW- Seeds weight (gm); SPP- Seeds per pod; **- highly significant at $p < 0.001$; ns- not significant at $p < 0.001$; SV- Sources of variation; R- Replication; T- Treatment duration (hrs); C- Concentration of colchicine (%); SD- Standard deviation and CV- Coefficient of variation (%).

Average growth characters of treatment durations and concentration levels

Table 3 provides the average values for growth metrics based on different treatment durations and colchicine concentrations. The findings reveal that the duration of treatment significantly ($p < 0.05$) impacted several growth parameters, including leaf count, nodes on the main branch, percentage germination, plant height, survival rate, terminal leaf width, and terminal leaf length. However, there was no significant effect on the number of main branches. Among the treatment durations, 2 hours yielded the highest leaf count (68.42) and terminal leaf width (7.73 cm), while the lowest values for these metrics were recorded at 0 hours (control) and 4 hours, respectively. The control (0 hours) also had the highest counts for nodes on the main branch (7.58), percentage germination (83.3%), plant height (21.38 cm), and

survival rate (72.90%). On the other hand, the 4-hour treatment duration resulted in the lowest node count on the main branch (6.00) and terminal leaf width (6.70 cm). Treatment duration of 6 hours produced the longest terminal leaf length (13.07 cm), whereas the control had the shortest (11.54 cm). Also, varying colchicine concentrations significantly affected the number of leaves, germination rate, and survival rate, but did not alter the number of main branches, nodes on the main branch, terminal leaf width, and terminal leaf length. The highest leaf count (69.75) was observed at a 0.05% concentration, while the lowest (61.42) occurred at 0.00% (control). The highest percentage of germination (85.4%) was observed at 0.00% concentration, with the lowest (47.9%) at 0.10%. The control concentration (0.00%) also had the highest survival rate (79.2%).

Table 3: Mean growth characters for four treatment durations and four concentration levels.

TIME (Hrs.)	NLV	NMB	NNB	PCG (%)	PHT (cm)	SVP (%)	TLB (cm)	TLL (cm)
0	62.00 ^b	7.00 ^a	7.58 ^a	83.3 ^a	21.38 ^a	72.90 ^a	7.58 ^a	11.54 ^b
2	68.42 ^a	6.83 ^a	7.25 ^a	62.5 ^b	18.38 ^b	58.3 ^b	7.73 ^a	12.82 ^a
4	67.75 ^a	6.83 ^a	6.00 ^c	41.7 ^c	17.45 ^b	39.6 ^c	6.70 ^b	13.07 ^a
6	68.33 ^a	6.75 ^a	6.50 ^b	39.6 ^c	17.20 ^b	37.5 ^c	7.01 ^b	13.20 ^a
LSD	0.97	0.58	0.42	9.32	1.37	6.64	0.34	1.175
Concentration (%)								
0.00	61.42 ^c	7.00 ^a	7.25 ^a	85.4 ^a	20.96 ^a	79.2 ^a	7.48 ^a	11.62 ^a
0.05	69.75 ^a	7.00 ^a	6.83 ^a	50.0 ^b	18.32 ^a	47.9 ^b	6.93 ^a	12.09 ^a
0.10	67.83 ^b	6.83 ^a	6.50 ^a	47.9 ^b	17.83 ^a	45.8 ^b	7.27 ^a	13.94 ^a
0.15	67.50 ^b	6.58 ^a	6.75 ^a	4.8 ^b	17.30 ^a	35.4 ^c	7.33 ^a	12.97 ^a
LSD	0.97	0.58	0.42	9.32	2.74	6.64	0.34	1.175

Remarks: Means with the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$ using the Least Significant Difference (LSD). Time (hrs) indicates treatment duration; Concentration (%) indicates concentration of colchicine; NLV- Number of leaves; NMB- Number of main branches; NNB- Number of nodes on the main branch; PCG- Percentage germination (%); PHT - Plant height (cm); SVP- Survival percentage (%); TLB- Terminal leaf breadth (cm) and TLL- Terminal leaf length (cm).

Average yield characters across various treatment durations and concentration levels of cowpea

Table 4 summarizes the average growth and yield characters for different treatment durations and colchicine concentrations. The results indicate that treatment duration significantly affects days to first flowering, pod count per plant, 100 seed weight, and seeds per pod. The 6-hour treatment duration resulted in the longest time to first flowering (58.17 days) and the highest 100-seed weight (22.38 g). In contrast, the control (0-hour duration) had the shortest days to flowering (54.50) and the lowest 100-seed weight (21.58 g). The control also produced the highest pod count per plant (22.25) and seeds per pod (22.25), whereas

the 6-hour treatment led to the lowest pod count per plant (18.67) and seeds per pod (18.75). The different colchicine concentrations significantly influenced days to first flowering, pod count per plant, 100-seed weight, and seeds per pod. A concentration of 0.15% resulted in the longest time to first flowering (58.25 days) and the highest 100-seed weight (22.39 g), while the control (0.00% concentration) had the shortest days to flowering (54.83) and the lowest 100-seed weight (21.72 g). The control concentration also yielded the highest pod count per plant (21.92) and seeds per pod (21.83), while the 0.15% concentration resulted in the lowest pod count per plant (18.08) and seeds per pod (18.33).

Table 4: Mean growth and yield characters for four treatment durations and four concentration levels

Time (Hrs)	Days to first flowering	Number of pods per plant	100-Seeds weight (gm)	Seeds per pod
0	54.50 ^b	22.25 ^a	21.58 ^b	22.25 ^a
2	57.75 ^a	20.42 ^b	22.36 ^a	20.00 ^a
4	58.08 ^a	20.08 ^b	22.34 ^a	20.17 ^a
6	58.17 ^a	18.67 ^c	22.38 ^a	18.75 ^b
LSD	0.76	0.73	0.20	0.64
Concentration (%)				
0.00	54.83 ^b	21.92 ^a	21.72 ^b	21.83 ^a
0.05	57.33 ^a	21.25 ^a	22.26 ^a	21.08 ^b
0.10	58.08 ^a	20.17 ^b	22.30 ^a	19.92 ^c
0.15	58.25 ^a	18.08 ^c	22.39 ^a	18.33 ^d
LSD	0.76	0.73	0.20	0.64

Remarks: Means with the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$ using the Least Significant Difference (LSD). Time (hrs) indicates treatment duration, Concentration (%) indicates concentration of colchicine, DFF- Days to first flowering; NPP- Number of pods per plant; SDW- Seeds weight (gm) and SPP- Seeds per pod.

Effect of treatment duration and colchicine concentration on cowpea growth characteristics

Interaction between treatment duration and colchicine concentration on number of leaves, number of main branches and number of nodes on main branches

Analysis shows no significant interaction between colchicine concentration and treatment duration regarding leaf count (Table 5). Variations were observed across different treatment conditions, with the control (0 hours, 0%) yielding 62.00 leaves and the highest count of 72.67 leaves observed at 6 hours with 0.05% colchicine. Although the treatment influenced leaf count, these changes were not statistically significant. Colchicine treatment had no significant effect on the number of main branches. Statistical analysis revealed no

notable interaction between treatment duration and colchicine concentration for this metric. The main branches' number remained relatively stable, ranging from 6.33 to 7.33 across all treatments. The control (0 hrs, 0%) had 7.33 branches, similar to the 4-hour treatment at 0.10% concentration, which had 6.67 branches. The number of nodes on the main branch showed no significant effect from colchicine treatment. There was no substantial interaction between treatment duration and colchicine concentration. The number of nodes ranged from 5.67 to 7.67, with the control treatment (0 hrs, 0%) having 7.33 nodes. The data suggest that colchicine treatment does not significantly alter the number of nodes on the main branch.

Table 5: Mean for interaction between treatment duration (hrs) and colchicine concentration (%) on numbers of leaves, main branches and nodes on main branches

T	X	<u>Number of leaves</u>				<u>Number of main branches</u>				<u>Number of nodes on main branches</u>			
		0.01 %	0.05 %	0.10 %	0.15 %	0 %	0.05 %	0.10 %	0.1 %	5 %	0 %	0.05 %	0.10 %
0	C	62.0	62.0	61.6	62.3	7.3	6.67	7.33	6.6	7.33	7.67	7.67	7.6
2	Hrs	0b	0b	7b	3b	3a	a	a	7a	a	a	a	7a
4	Hrs	0b	7a	7a	3a	7a	a	a	7a	a	a	a	3a
6	Hrs	0b	7a	7a	7a	0a	a	a	7a	a	a	a	7a
LSD		1.94				1.1				0.83			
		6				61				38			

Remarks: Means with the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$ using the Least Significant Difference (LSD). T: Treatment duration (hrs). C: Colchicine concentration (%).

Interaction between treatment duration and colchicine concentration on germination percentage, plant height and survival percentage

Table 6 highlights a significant decline in germination percentage with increased treatment duration and colchicine concentration. The control (0 hrs, 0%) achieved percentage germination of 83.3%, whereas 6 hours of treatment with 0.15% colchicine reduced the percentage germination to 25.0%. This indicates that prolonged exposure and higher concentrations of colchicine adversely affect seed germination. Plant height

decreased with longer treatment durations and higher colchicine concentrations. The control (0 hrs, 0%) had a height of 75.0 cm, while 6 hours at 0.15% colchicine resulted in a reduced height of 25.0 cm. It suggests that colchicine exposure inhibits plant growth, leading to shorter plants. The survival percentage significantly decreased with longer treatment durations. The control treatment (0 hrs, 0%) had a survival rate of 75.0%, which dropped to 25.0% with 6 hours of 0.15% colchicine. This underscores the negative impact of extended colchicine exposure on plant survival.

Table 6: Mean for interaction between treatment duration (hrs) and colchicine concentration on percentage germination, plant height and survival percentage

T	X	Percentage germination (%)				Plant height (cm)				Survival percentage (%)			
		0 %	0.05 %	0.10 %	0.15 %	0 %	0.05 %	0.10 %	0.15 %	0 %	0.05 %	0.10 %	0.15 %
0	Hrs	83.	83.3	83.3	83.3	21.4	21.3	21.3	21.4	75.	75.	75.	66.7
		3a	a	a	a	3a	7a	0a	3a	0a	0a	0a	a
2	Hrs	83.	66.7	58.3	41.7	20.5	18.3	18.0	16.7	83.	66.	58.	25.0
		3a	a	a	a	0a	0a	3a	0a	3a	7a	3a	b
4	Hrs	91.	25.0	25.0	25.0	20.5	17.0	16.3	15.9	83.	25.	25.	25.0
		7a	a	a	a	0a	3a	0a	7a	3a	0b	0b	b
6	Hrs	83.	25.0	25.0	25.0	21.4	16.6	15.7	15.1	75.	25.	25.	25.0
		3a	a	a	a	0a	0a	0a	0a	0a	0b	0b	b
LSD		18.				2.74				13.			
		64				0				27			

Remarks: Means with the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$ using the Least Significant Difference (LSD). T: Treatment duration (hrs). C: Colchicine concentration (%).

Interaction between treatment duration and colchicine concentration on terminal leaf breadth and terminal leaf length

Table 7 indicates no significant effect of colchicine treatment on terminal leaf

breadth. The leaf breadth remained consistent across various treatments, with the control (0 hrs, 0%) measuring 7.50cm and a treatment of 6 hours at 0.10% yielding a leaf breadth of 6.30 cm. These results

suggest that colchicine treatment does not notably affect terminal leaf breadth. While colchicine treatment caused some variation in terminal leaf length, these changes were not statistically significant. The control (0 hrs, 0%) had a leaf length of 11.50 cm. The longest length (14.67 cm) was observed at 6 hours with 0.15% colchicine. It suggests

that colchicine has a minor impact on leaf length, but the effect is insignificant. Treatment duration and colchicine concentration primarily influence germination and survival rates, while other growth characteristics show relatively stable responses across different treatment conditions.

Table 7: Mean for interaction between treatment duration (hrs) and colchicine concentration on terminal leaf breadth and leaf length

T X C	Terminal leaf breadth (cm)				Terminal leaf length (cm)			
	0 %	0.05%	0.10%	0.15%	0 %	0.05 %	0.10 %	0.15 %
0 Hrs	7.53a	7.50a	7.63a	7.63a	11.50a	11.27a	11.70a	11.70a
2 Hrs	7.50a	7.63a	7.93a	7.83a	11.80a	13.10a	14.97a	11.40a
4 Hrs	7.40a	6.30a	6.60a	6.50a	11.57a	12.30a	14.30a	14.10a
6 Hrs	7.50a	6.30a	6.90a	7.33a	11.63a	11.70a	14.80a	14.67a
LSD	0.676				2.350			
	6							

Remarks: Means with the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$ using the Least Significant Difference (LSD). T: Treatment duration (hrs). C: Colchicine concentration (%).

Effect of treatment duration and colchicine concentration on cowpea yield characters

Interaction between treatment duration and colchicine concentration on days to first flowering and number of pods per plant

Table 8 shows that the interaction between colchicine concentration and treatment duration did not significantly affect the days to first flowering. The control treatment (0 hrs, 0%) had an average of 55.00 days to first flowering and was consistent across most treatments. Days to flowering ranged between 54.00 and 59.67 across different

conditions, indicating that colchicine treatment does not significantly influence the timing of flowering. There is an insignificant interaction between colchicine concentration and treatment duration on the number of pods per plant. However, a general trend showed a decline in pod count with higher concentrations and longer treatment durations. The control (0 hrs, 0%) had 22.33 pods per plant, while 6 hours at 0.15% colchicine resulted in 12.67 pods per plant. These findings suggest that higher concentrations and extensive exposure negatively affect pod production.

Table 8: Mean for interaction between treatment duration (hrs) and colchicine concentration on days to first flowering and number of pods per plant

T X C	Days to first flowering				Number of pods per plant			
	0 %	0.05 %	0.10 %	0.15 %	0 %	0.05 %	0.10 %	0.15 %
0 Hrs	55.00 b	54.00 b	55.00b	54.00b	22.33a	22.67a	22.00a	22.00a
2 Hrs	54.67 b	58.33 a	58.33a	59.67a	22.00a	20.67b	19.67b	19.33b
4 Hrs	54.67 b	58.67 a	59.33a	59.67a	21.67b	21.00b	19.33b	18.33b
6 Hrs	55.00 b	58.33 a	59.67a	59.67a	21.67b	20.67b	19.67b	12.67c
LSD	1.517				1.459			

Remarks: Means with the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$ using the Least Significant Difference (LSD). T: Treatment duration (hrs). C: Colchicine concentration (%).

Interaction between treatment duration and colchicine concentration on seed weight and number of seeds per pod

Table 9 indicates that colchicine concentration and treatment duration did not significantly affect seed weight. The control treatment (0 hrs, 0%) had an average seed weight of 21.53 g, with minor variations across treatments. The highest seed weight (22.70 g) was at 6 hours with 0.10% colchicine. These results imply that

changes in colchicine concentration and treatment duration do not significantly impact seed weight. There is no significant effect of colchicine treatment on the number of seeds per pod. The control (0 hrs, 0%) had 22.00 seeds per pod. The highest count (22.70 seeds per pod) was noted at 6 hours with 0.10% colchicine. These results suggest that colchicine treatment does not significantly alter the number of seeds per pod.

Table 9: Mean for interaction between treatment duration (hrs) and colchicine concentration on seeds weight and seeds per pod

T X C	Seed weight (gm)				Seeds per pod			
	0 %	0.05 %	0.10 %	0.15 %	0 %	0.05 %	0.10 %	0.15 %
0 Hrs	21.53b	21.90 b	21.27b	21.63 b	22.00a	22.33a	22.33a	22.33a
2 Hrs	21.77b	22.40 a	22.63a	22.63 a	21.67a	20.67a	18.67a	19.00a
4 Hrs	21.80b	22.37 a	22.60a	22.60 a	21.67a	21.00a	19.33a	18.67a
6 Hrs	21.77b	22.37 a	22.70a	22.70 a	22.00a	20.33a	19.33a	13.33b
LSD	0.4070				1.281			

Remarks: Means with the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at $P > 0.05$ using the Least Significant Difference (LSD). T: Treatment duration (hrs). C: Colchicine concentration (%).

Correlation analysis of growth and yield characters in cowpea

Table 10 presents the correlation coefficients for various growth and yield traits of cowpea. The analysis reveals strong positive and negative correlations among different traits, indicating how changes in one characteristic can influence others. The number of leaves exhibits a strong positive correlation with days to first flowering (0.87), suggesting that an increase in the number of leaves is associated with a higher period before flowering occurs. Similarly, 100-seed weight is positively correlated with number of leaves (0.80) and percentage germination (0.75), indicating that plants with more leaves and higher germination rates tend to produce heavier seeds. The number of pods per plant has a positive correlation with seeds per pod (0.89), meaning that more pods generally result in more seeds per pod. On the other hand, days to first flowering show a strong negative correlation with percentage germination (-0.81), plant height (-0.78), and survival percentage (-0.85), suggesting that earlier flowering is associated with lower germination rates,

shorter plant height, and reduced survival rates. Plant height also negatively correlates with number of nodes on the main branch (-0.64) and 100 seed weight (-0.74), indicating that taller plants may have fewer pods and lighter seeds. The number of nodes on the main branch has a positive correlation with the number of main branches (0.36) but negative correlations with Days to first flowering (-0.61) and percentage germination (-0.52), implying that more nodes are associated with delayed flowering and decreased germination. Terminal leaf breadth shows a positive correlation with the number of nodes on the main branch (0.58) but a negative correlation with the number of nodes on the main branch (-0.49), suggesting that wider leaves might correspond to fewer pods. Similarly, terminal leaf length negatively correlates with the number of nodes on the main branch (-0.49), indicating that longer leaves might be associated with a reduction in the number of pods. The strongest positive correlation (0.94) is observed between survival percentage and percentage germination, highlighting a close relationship between these two traits.

Table 10: Correlation coefficient parameters for growth and yield characters of cowpea determined under four levels of colchicine concentration and treatment duration

	DFF	NLV	NM B	NNB	NPP	PCG	PHT	SDW	SPP	SVP	TL B	TLL
DFF	1.00											
NLV	0.87 ***	1.00										
NM B	- 0.15 **	- 0.07ns	1.00									
NNB	- 0.61 ***	- 0.52* **	0.36 ***	1.00								
NPP	- 0.65 ***	- 0.51* **	0.19 **	0.41. 00***	1.00							
PCG	- 0.81 ***	- 0.77* **	0.14 **	0.63* **	0.59* **	1.00						
PHT	- 0.78 ***	- 0.74* **	0.19 **	0.54* **	0.61* **	0.74 ***	1.00					
SD W	- 0.85 ***	- 0.80* **	- 0.25 **	- 0.53* **	- 0.64* **	0.75 ***	0.74* **	- 1.00				
SPP	- 0.68 ***	- 0.52* **	0.21 **	0.38* **	0.89* **	0.64 ***	0.65* **	0.69 ***	1.00			
SVP	- 0.85 ***	- 0.76* **	0.15 **	0.63* **	0.58* **	0.94 ***	0.74* **	0.74 ***	0.62 ***	1.0 0		
TLB	- 0.40 ***	- 0.40* **	0.15 **	0.58* **	0.13* *	0.55 ***	0.42* **	0.24 **	0.09 ns	0.5 2**	1.0 0	
TLL	- 0.45 ***	- 0.45* **	- 0.17 **	- 0.40* **	- 0.49* **	- 0.49 ***	- 0.51* **	- 0.54 ***	- 0.53 ***	- 0.3 9**	0.0 8n	1.0 0

*, **, *** and ns means significant at $p < 0.05$, 0.01, 0.001 and not significant respectively.

DFF: Days to first flowering, NLV: Number of leaves, NMB: Number of main branches, NNB: Number of nodes on the main branch, NPP: Number of pods per plant, PCG: Percentage germination, PHT: Plant height, SDW: 100 seed weight, SPP: Seeds per pod, SVP: Survival percentage, TLB: Terminal leaf breadth, and TLL: Terminal leaf length.

DISCUSSION

Colchicine treatment profoundly affected cowpea growth and yield, with the intensity of the treatments (concentration and exposure time) playing a significant role in response. As the dosage and exposure period increased, growth characteristics that were reduced were germination rate, plant height, survival rate, and the number of nodes on the main stem. A decrease in percentage germination and survival rate due to colchicine treatments agrees with the findings of many researchers on cowpea (Kumar et al; 2009), showing that higher colchicine concentrations can hinder normal plant development. The decline in germination is attributed to colchicine disrupting protein function, hampering early plant growth (Fiaz et al., 2021). This effect of chemical mutagens on reducing germination is a well-documented phenomenon (Bhatia et al., 2021).

Regarding plant survival, prolonged colchicine exposure and higher doses considerably decreased the survival rates of cowpea seedlings. Prolonged exposure likely interferes with essential cellular processes, reducing seedling vigour and increasing mortality (Zhang et al., 2020). Colchicine-induced reductions in plant height, especially with longer treatments, are commonly observed in M1 generation plants due to decreased cell division and chromosomal abnormalities (Rogers et al., 2021).

One positive outcome increased was the number of leaves, especially at lower colchicine concentrations (0.05%) and shorter exposure times (2 hours). This increase in leaf production could enhance photosynthesis, improving its ability to produce seeds (Singh et al., 2023). Colchicine-treated plants appeared to develop thicker, broader leaves and larger stomata, which could improve gas exchange efficiency (Nair et al., 2022). Colchicine altered several traits, including days to first flowering, number of pods, seed

weight, and seeds per pod. The highest seed weight was a 6-hour treatment and a concentration of 0.15%, similar to earlier studies (Rahman et al., 2022). However, colchicine negatively impacted the number of pods per plant and seeds per pod. The reduction in reproductive performance could be associated with colchicine's toxic effects, which inhibit enzyme function and disrupt reproductive processes (Nair et al., 2023). Seed sterility and fewer pods are frequently observed in mutagenic treatments due to biochemical imbalances in the plant (Kumar et al., 2022), as seen in crops like soybeans (Ali et al., 2023).

Correlation analysis provided insights into the relationships between various growth and yield traits. The results showed that plants with more leaves tended to flower later, as indicated by a positive correlation between days to first flowering and leaf number. In contrast, days to flowering negatively correlated with germination rate, plant height, and survival, suggesting that plants that flower earlier are often shorter and have better germination and survival rates. Leaf number was positively linked with seed weight, implying that plants with more leaves tend to produce heavier seeds, though these plants might produce fewer pods.

Plant height also showed a trade-off with reproductive traits, as taller plants had fewer pods and lighter seeds. The number of pods per plant was positively correlated with seeds per pod, meaning that plants with more pods generally had more seeds, which is advantageous for yield. Additionally, germination rate had a negative correlation with days to flowering but a positive relationship with seed weight, suggesting that better germination is associated with delayed flowering and heavier seeds. Lastly, broader terminal leaves correlated positively with the number of nodes on the main stem, while longer leaves were associated with fewer pods.

CONCLUSION

The study highlights how colchicine treatment influences cowpea growth and yield, where the concentration and duration of exposure play a significant role. Higher colchicine concentrations and longer treatment durations led to reduced germination rates, survival, plant height, and node count, corroborating prior research on other crops like black gram and soybeans. This reduction may be due to colchicine's interference with protein function and seedling vigour, as well as chromosomal abnormalities. Colchicine increased the number of leaves per plant, especially at lower concentrations (0.05%) and shorter treatment durations (2 hours), enhancing leaf area, which could improve

photosynthesis and seed yield. Correlation analysis revealed positive associations between the number of leaves and seed weight, suggesting that more leaves lead to heavier seeds. Despite some positive growth traits, colchicine reduced the number of pods per plant and seeds per pod. Enzyme inhibition and mutagen-induced toxicity are likely responsible for this decline, as observed in other studies. Longer days to flowering were associated with more leaves but fewer pods and lower overall yield. Early flowering correlated with lower germination, shorter plant height, and reduced survival. Taller plants had fewer pods and lighter seeds, indicating a trade-off between vegetative growth and reproductive traits.

REFERENCES

- Ali, S., Khan, M. and Rizwan, M. (2023). Influence of colchicine on growth and reproductive traits in soybean. *Journal of Plant Growth Regulation*. 42(1), 1–12.
- Bhatia, V., Shukla, P. and Agarwal, M. (2021). Chemical mutagens and their impact on seed germination: A review. *Plant Science Today*. 8(1), 75–84.
- Dillard, C.J. and German, J.B. (2000). Phytochemicals: nutraceuticals and human health. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*. 80(12), 1744–1756.
- Dugje, I.Y., Omoigui, L.O., Ekeleme, F., Bandyopadhyay, R., Kumar, P.L. and Kamara, A.Y. (2009). Farmers' guide to cowpea production in West Africa. IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria. Available at <https://www.iita.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Farmers-guide-to-cowpea-production.pdf>
- Fatokun, C.A., Danesh, D., Young, N.D. and Singh, B.B. (2018). Molecular genetics and breeding of cowpea. *Plant Genetics* 34(6). 931–945.
- Fiaz, S., Ahmad, M. and Khan, M. (2021). Colchicine and its effects on protein function in plants. *Journal of Agricultural Science*. 13(4), 241–250. Available at <https://www-naweb.iaea.org/nafa/pbg/plant-mutation-breeding-database.html>
- Jankowicz-Cieslak, J., Tai, T.H., Kumlehn, J. and Till, B.J. (2017). *Biotechnologies for plant mutation breeding: Protocols*. Springer. <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9783319558585>.
- Kumar, V.A; Kumari, R.U; Amutha, R; Kumar, T.S; Hepziba, S.J and Kumar, C.R.A. (2009). Effect of chemical mutagen on expression of characters in arid legume pulse – cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp.). *Research Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*. 5 (6), 1115–1120.
- Kumar, A., Sharma, P. and Singh, K. (2022). Impact of colchicine on pod production and seed quality in legumes. *Journal of Plant Research*. 135(5), 789–798.
- Nair, P., Lakshmanan, R. and Varghese, S. (2022). Effects of colchicine on leaf morphology and stomatal characteristics in cowpea. *Plant Mutation Reports*. 14(3), 189–198.
- Nair, R., Rajput, S. and Pillai, S. (2023). Colchicine-induced changes in cowpea growth and yield. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*. 26(1), 115–126.
- Rahman, M., Alam, M. and Hasan, M. (2022). Optimal colchicine treatment for enhancing seed weight in cowpea. *Journal of Plant Growth Regulation*. 41(2), 323–332.
- Rogers, D., Fong, Y., and Roberts, A. (2021). Colchicine-induced chromosomal abnormalities and their impact on plant growth. *Plant Genetic Resources*. 19(4), 337–348.
- Sattin, M., Baldini, M. and Bocchi, S. (2019). Induced polyploidy in forage legumes. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 10: 231–241.
- Singh, B.B., Ajeigbe, H.A. and Tarawali, S.A. (2021a). Improving the Productivity of cowpea in dry areas of sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 58(2), 89–96.
- Singh, B.B., Sharma, M. and Singh, R.
-

- (2021b). Breeding strategies for cowpea improvement. *Journal of Crop Improvement*, 35(3), 439–457.
- Singh, V., Singh, P. and Sharma, A. (2023). Effects of colchicine on leaf area and seed yield in cowpea. *Journal of Crop Science and Technology*. 15(1), 65–74.
- Zhang, J., Li, Y. and Wang, Y. (2020). Impact of colchicine on seedling vigor and mortality in various crops. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*. 28(6), 453–464.
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